

EXPLORING DIVERSIFICATION IN INDIAN AGRICULTURE: EVIDENCE FROM INDIA'S RECENT DECADE

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Abstract

Agriculture diversification encompasses a range of activities apart from crops, and this diversification is an important strategy in addressing the issues confronting the agricultural sector of India. Some of these issues include climate change, market volatility, and risk reduction. This paper explores the trend and intensity of agricultural and crop diversification in India from 2014-15 to 2023-24. The study is based on secondary data from government reports, namely the Economic Survey and the Agriculture Statistics. The study focuses on the contribution made by crops, livestock, forestry, and fisheries to Gross Value Added in the sector. The two statistical tools have been used to measure crop diversification i.e., the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) and Simpson's Index of Diversification (SID). The findings of the study indicate that in the last ten years, the process of diversification has constantly increased crop diversification as well as the diversification of agricultural activities as it reflects a constant downward shift of HHI and the SID is increasing accordingly. These are a testament to the increased significance of diversification in the agriculture sector which not only enhances its resilience to climate change but also the stability of farm earnings.

Keywords: *Agricultural Diversification, Crop Diversification, Pattern of diversification, Extent of diversification, Herfindahl-Hirschman Index*

Introduction

Agricultural diversification refers to the process by which farmers increase the variety of agricultural products they produce. Instead of focusing on a single crop or livestock species,

farmers diversify by cultivating multiple crops, raising different types of livestock, or integrating other agricultural activities such as aquaculture or agroforestry. There is a stark differentiation between agriculture diversification and crop diversification. Agriculture diversification includes practising multiple activities like crop cultivation, aquaculture, livestock rearing and forestry (Saikia and Gogoi, 2017). On the other hand, crop diversification is the process of cultivating more than one kind of crop on a farm or in a particular area, as opposed to depending on just one. Enhancing sustainability, lowering risk, and fostering general resilience in the face of several obstacles like pests, illnesses, shifting weather patterns, and market swings are the objectives of this agricultural strategy. Crop diversity can be achieved in a number of ways, such as through crop rotations (growing different crops in the same field sequentially), agroforestry (growing trees and shrubs alongside crops), and intercropping (growing different crops in the same field simultaneously). These methods can help create more resilient and sustainable agricultural systems, but their implementation necessitates careful planning and consideration of local conditions. In India, crop diversification has become more significant as a tactic to deal with the different issues the nation's agriculture sector is facing. India has historically had an agrarian economy, with agriculture providing the majority of jobs for those living in rural areas. Historically, monoculture has been practised in many parts of India, with a strong reliance on a small number of key crops, such as wheat and rice. With this strategy, agriculture becomes more susceptible to the dangers of a single-crop system, such as pest and disease vulnerability and market volatility (Belete and Yadete, 2023). The Indian government has put in place a number of programs and initiatives to encourage the cultivation of a wide variety of crops in recognition of the need for crop diversity. Indian agriculture is gradually diversifying towards high-value crops in order to meet the increasing domestic demand and gain from globalisation (Anuja et al., 2020). The rapid rise in the consumption of high-value food commodities indicates the great demand potential for high-value crops in India (Kumar et al., 2003). These initiatives seek to give farmers the resources and assistance they need while also educating them about the advantages of diversification. India has many different agro-climatic zones, making it possible to grow a large variety of crops there. Because different crops may have differing tolerances to temperature, rainfall, and other climatic conditions, agricultural diversification is especially important in the context of climate change. Strategies for agricultural diversification, like encouraging drought-tolerant plants and effective irrigation techniques, help ensure sustainable water use (Mukherjee, 2021).

Crop diversification lowers the financial risks associated with relying just on one crop, which in turn improves farmers' livelihood stability. It also encourages a more robust agricultural system and gives them access to alternate forms of income. Crop diversification has a big financial impact on the economy overall as well as on farmers. Reducing risk is one of the main economic benefits of crop diversification. Farmers can lessen the effects of crop failures or price swings related to a particular crop and increase sustainability by planting a diversity of crops (Feliciano, 2018). Farmers can diversify their sources of income by growing different crops. Even if one crop has difficulties, others might continue to thrive and offer a more steady and consistent source of revenue all year long. Farmers have the opportunity to access a variety of markets by cultivating a broad agricultural base. Farmers are better able to meet the diverse needs of their customers and react to market movements when they vary their product offerings. Better pricing and market access may result from this flexibility, which would ultimately increase farmers' financial gains. Throughout the year, diversified farming systems frequently need a wider range of labour and abilities. This may result in more work prospects in rural areas, promoting regional economic growth and reducing poverty (Satyasai and Viswanathan, 1997). The nutrient requirements and growth patterns of different crops vary. A more effective use of resources like water, soil nutrients, and sunlight is made possible by crop variety. Increased productivity and cost savings from this optimization can boost agriculture's overall economic efficiency. Diversified agricultural systems can act as insurance against the growing risks associated with climate change. Crop resilience to climatic pressures can vary, acting as a buffer against extreme weather occurrences and boosting agricultural resilience overall.

Literature Review

A study by Kumar et al (2012) found that diversification of agriculture towards high-value crops is crucial for increasing farm income, creating employment, reducing poverty, and conserving resources. Their study in eastern India shows a slow shift towards high-value crops, with technology, education, and infrastructure playing key roles. In addition to agro-climatic factors, the paper's regression results have highlighted the significance of technology, contemporary tools, education, and road connection as key predictors of agricultural diversification towards high-value crops.

Prajapat and Kaswan (2022) in their paper have clearly mentioned that crop diversification is crucial for Indian agriculture to address food and nutritional security, poverty alleviation, and sustainable growth. Factors such as resource-related, technology-related, household-related,

price-related, and institutional and infrastructure-related factors influence crop diversification. The researchers have pointed out that few crops are occupying major production area and are grown repeatedly year after year. As a consequence, biotic and abiotic restrictions have emerged at multiple field levels, and the overall benefits of farming have decreased. This has resulted in an urgent need to implement crop diversification in order to reap the benefits of farming.

The research paper by Dalal and Shankar (2022) emphasizes the importance of crop diversification in India. According to the paper, crop diversification can provide employment and income opportunities throughout the year, benefiting small and marginal farmers. Diversification allows a shift from low-profit to high-profit cropping systems, increasing production, quality, and earnings for farmers. The paper outlines various approaches to crop diversification, such as horizontal diversification, crop substitution, and integrating horticulture, agroforestry, and livestock components. The paper notes some constraints to crop diversification, such as poor infrastructure, lack of access to inputs, and low farmer awareness, but emphasizes its growing importance and future potential in Indian agriculture.

Sanjeev Kumar (2022) in his paper studied the emerging trends and patterns of crop diversification in the Indian state of Uttar Pradesh from 2000-01 to 2019-20. The author analyzed the compound annual growth rates (CAGR) of various agricultural parameters like area, production and yield at the crop group level and regional level within Uttar Pradesh. The research found that Uttar Pradesh is witnessing a shift from traditional food grain crops to high-value crops, but this shift is not evenly distributed across the different regions of the state. The Western Uttar Pradesh region has the highest level of crop diversification, followed by Central Uttar Pradesh, Bundelkhand, and Eastern Uttar Pradesh. This study suggests that policy support in terms of enhanced rural infrastructure and appropriate technology is needed to promote crop diversification and enhance farmers' incomes across all regions of Uttar Pradesh.

The study by Mukherjee and Chattopadhyay (2017) in their paper *Crop Diversification in West Bengal: A District Level Analysis for The Period 1980-81 to 2011-12* examined the dynamics of crop diversification in West Bengal, India, during the pre and post-liberalization period. The paper addressed questions on the nature and scope of crop diversification in a small farm-dominated economy like West Bengal and the factors influencing it. The researchers' analysis reflected the positive impact of operational area and cropping intensity on the degree of crop diversification. In contrast, factors like availability of irrigation

facilities, degree of electrification, usage of fertilizers and output price have a negative influence on crop diversification in a particular region. The study also pointed out that a high level of diversification in an area does not necessarily correspond to the district having a traditional resource base or a high endowment of modern inputs. The study also found that there is a significant inter-district variation in the degree of crop diversification during the period under consideration. It implies that a low-yielding basket of crops may be the result of need-induced diversification in resource-constrained areas.

Research by Dasgupta and Bhaumik (2014) explored the crop sector diversification in West Bengal, India from 1980-81 to 2009-10, focusing on the impact of this diversification on agricultural output growth. The study revealed that West Bengal's agriculture had shifted from traditional food grain crops like aus, aman, and pulses to boro rice, oilseeds, and potatoes, accelerating post-globalization after 1995-96. This diversification has positively impacted agricultural output growth, with yield growth being the largest contributor. Small and marginal farmers have played a crucial role in driving diversification and maintaining a diversified crop portfolio to mitigate risks. The expansion of irrigation and increased fertilizer use have facilitated this process, enabling yield growth in both food and non-food grain crops.

Malik and Singh (2002) in their paper analysed crop diversification at the district level in the state of Haryana. The researchers used two measures of crop diversification - the Crop Diversification Index (CDI) and the Entropy Index (EI) - to analyze the extent of diversification across different districts of Haryana from 1980-81 to 1996-97. The study found that the Ambala and Mohindergarh districts showed a decrease in CDI during 1990-91, indicating a movement towards specialization, but this trend reversed in the later period. Additionally, the CDI increased in Kurukshetra, Sonapat, Rohtak, Gurgaon, Faridabad, and Bhiwani districts, indicating a shift towards more lucrative crops. The Entropy Index results showed a similar pattern, with Ambala and Mohindergarh districts showing reduced diversification initially, followed by an increase later on. Whereas, Kaithal, Karnal, Panipat, Rewari, Jind, Hisar, and Sirsa districts registered a decline in EI, indicating reduced diversification. The analysis suggested that crop diversification was more prominent in some districts due to proximity to the metropolitan city of Delhi, availability of markets, and increased demand for high-value crops like vegetables, fruits, and flowers.

Objectives

1. To examine the trends in agricultural diversification in India.
2. To examine the diversification patterns of crops and discern trends.
3. To assess the levels of crop diversity in India, including the variety and distribution of crops planted across various agricultural zones.
4. To assess the extent of diversification in agriculture and related sectors, including livestock, fisheries, and agro-industries, therefore elucidating their impact on the evolving agricultural landscapes in India.

Methodology

The research will be conducted with the help of secondary data from various Government sources and reports such as Agriculture Statistics at a Glance 2022, Basic Animal Husbandry Statistics 2023 and Economic Survey Report 2023-24. Tabular analysis was carried out to examine the pattern of diversification in India. In order to study the extent or magnitude of diversification, diversification index was used which is coherent and easily comprehensible. For finding the magnitude of diversification within crops and agriculture sector as a whole two statistical tools namely the Herfindahl Index and Simpson's Index was applied in this study. Two different indexes were tested for establishing consistency in the study. The calculation for both these indexes was rendered using spreadsheet.

Pattern of Agricultural Diversification

The agriculture sector comprises of four sub-sectors i.e., Crops, Livestocks, Forestry and Fisheries. The share of Agriculture sector in the Gross Value Added (GVA) increased from 18.5 per cent in 2011-12 to 19 per cent in 2021-22 (Table 1). The contribution of the sub-sectors in the Gross Value added (GVA) within the primary sector is very striking to observe. The share of crop sector in the GVA has reduced from 12.1 per cent in 2011-12 to 10.4 per cent in 2021-22 (Table 1). The contribution of Forestry and logging has remained almost constant during the same time period. However, the shares of Livestock and Fisheries in the total GVA have increased during 2011-12 to 2021-22. Livestock has increased from 4 per cent to 5.7 percent and Fisheries moved up from 0.8 per cent to 1.3 percent (Table 1).

Table 1: Sectoral share in Gross Value Added at Current Basic Prices (Figures in percentage)

S.No.	Industry	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20 @	2020-21*	2021-22`	2022-23#
I	Agriculture, forestry & fishing	18.5	18.2	18.6	18.2	17.7	18.0	18.3	17.6	18.3	20.3	19.0	21.1
	Crops	12.1	11.8	12.1	11.2	10.6	10.6	10.5	9.8	10.3	11.2	10.4	-
	Livestock	4.0	4.0	4.1	4.4	4.6	4.8	5.1	5.1	5.3	6.1	5.7	-
	Forestry and logging	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.6	1.5	-
	Fishing and aquaculture	0.8	0.9	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.1	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.3	-
II	Industry	32.5	31.8	30.8	30.0	30.0	29.3	29.2	29.1	26.9	27.3	28.5	32.5
	Mining and quarrying	3.2	3.1	2.9	2.7	2.3	2.3	2.2	2.2	1.9	1.7	2.0	2.7
	Manufacturing	17.4	17.1	16.5	16.3	17.1	16.7	16.6	16.4	14.7	15.4	15.8	16.9
	Electricity, gas, water supply & other utility services	2.3	2.3	2.5	2.5	2.7	2.5	2.7	2.6	2.7	2.8	2.6	3.5
	Construction	9.6	9.2	8.9	8.5	7.9	7.7	7.7	7.9	7.5	7.4	8.1	9.4
III	Services	49.0	50.0	50.6	51.8	52.3	52.6	52.5	53.3	54.8	52.4	52.5	46.4
	GVA at basic prices	100.0											

Source: Agriculture Statistics at a Glance 2022

The annual growth in the value of output for each of the sub-sectors within agriculture has been significant (Table 2). Moreover, to examine which sector has outperformed the others Compound Annual Growth Rate was calculated. Figure 1 represents the Compound Annual Growth Rate of each sector. Thus it becomes clear that Fisheries and Aquaculture has grown the maximum in terms of Value of output during the period 2011-12 to 2021-22.

Table 2: Value of Output in sub-sectors of Agriculture and Allied Activities at Current Prices (Rs. in Crores)

Year	Crop	Growth (%)	Livestock	Growth (%)	Fisheries	Growth (%)	Forestry and logging	Growth (%)
2011-12	1191483		487751	-	80105	-	148748	-
2012-13	1329582	11.59%	564937	15.82%	94297	17.72%	164356	10.49%
2013-14	1533426	15.33%	646178	14.38%	115309	22.28%	187083	13.83%
2014-15	1595498	4.05%	742807	14.95%	136229	18.14%	207931	11.14%
2015-16	1637236	2.62%	833498	12.21%	155690	14.29%	220421	6.01%
2016-17	1818832	11.09%	950677	14.06%	181580	16.63%	245415	11.34%
2017-18	1961181	7.83%	1043079	9.72%	226759	24.88%	259773	5.85%
2018-19	2047644	4.41%	1149783	10.23%	249107	9.86%	304551	17.24%
2019-20	2279651	11.33%	1276172	10.99%	275527	10.61%	321975	5.72%
2020-21	2466535	8.20%	1408652	10.38%	295504	7.25%	352179	9.38%
2021-22	2722201	10.37%	1563399	10.99%	338936	14.70%	382004	8.47%
CAGR (%)	8.61%	-	12.35%	-	15.52%	-	9.89%	-

Source: Author’s calculation with collated data from various Government sources

Figure 1: Sub-Sectoral Compound Annual Growth Rate in Value of Output

Source: Author’s analysis from Table 2

Pattern of Crop Diversification

On studying the pattern of crop diversification it is evident that the shares of Coarse Cereals, oilseeds and fibres in the Gross Cropped Area (GCA) have reduced. Coarse cereals have seen a reduction from 12.9 per cent to 11.52 per cent (Table 3). Whereas, oilseeds and fibres have reduced 14.81 per cent to 13.88 per cent and 6.8 per cent to 6.64 per cent respectively (Table 3). On the other hand, shares of pulses, fruits and vegetables in the GCA during the same period have increased. Share of pulses grew from 11.38 per cent to 12.49 per cent during 2012-13 to 2019-20. Area cultivated for fruits have increased from 2.1 per cent to 2.35 per cent and that of vegetables have increased from 2.88 to 3.17 per cent.

Table 3: Share of major Food crops, Cash crops and Horticultural crops in the Gross Cropped Area

Crop	Percentage Share of Area to Gross Cropped Area							
	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
Rice	21.98	22.10	22.32	21.91	22.15	22.45	22.58	22.77
Jowar	3.23	2.85	3.14	3.08	2.79	2.45	2.09	2.32
Bajra	3.90	3.98	3.76	3.61	3.77	3.75	3.60	3.59
Maize	4.41	4.48	4.39	4.29	4.57	4.43	4.44	4.61
Ragi	0.57	0.59	0.60	0.57	0.51	0.61	0.48	0.51
Wheat	15.70	15.60	16.16	15.66	15.98	15.52	15.71	16.80
Barley	0.37	0.35	0.36	0.27	0.29	0.27	0.24	0.26
Other Cereals & Millets	0.42	0.38	0.36	0.40	0.35	0.30	0.28	0.24
Coarse Cereals	12.90	12.64	12.61	12.21	12.27	11.82	11.13	11.52
Total Cereals	50.58	50.33	51.09	49.78	50.40	49.78	49.41	51.09
Gram	4.13	4.66	3.86	3.76	4.03	4.78	4.49	4.38
Tur	1.81	1.77	1.73	1.77	2.35	1.92	2.17	2.00
Other Pulses	5.44	5.47	5.34	6.05	6.84	7.31	7.09	6.12
Total Pulses	11.38	11.90	10.93	11.58	13.22	14.01	13.75	12.49
Total Food-grains	61.96	62.23	62.02	61.36	63.62	63.80	63.15	63.58
Sugarcane	2.80	2.75	2.80	2.71	2.38	2.54	2.77	2.48
Condiments & Spices	1.76	1.71	1.79	1.93	1.93	1.80	1.96	1.97
Total Fruits	2.10	2.05	2.11	2.22	2.22	2.24	2.39	2.35
Potatoes	0.85	0.84	0.89	0.97	0.93	0.91	0.91	0.87
Onions	0.27	0.30	0.34	0.58	0.55	0.52	0.51	0.57
Total Vegetables	2.88	2.87	3.05	3.40	3.33	3.27	3.21	3.17
Groundnut	2.55	2.58	2.38	2.27	2.63	2.44	2.35	2.31
Sesamum	0.87	0.82	0.88	1.01	0.93	0.87	0.82	0.80
Rapeseed & Mustard	3.07	2.98	2.74	2.82	2.81	2.77	3.08	2.92
Linseed	0.12	0.11	0.11	0.09	0.11	0.08	0.07	0.06

Other Oil Seeds	8.21	8.41	7.99	8.12	7.78	7.11	7.33	7.81
Total Oil Seeds	14.81	14.90	14.10	14.32	14.26	13.27	13.65	13.88
Cotton	6.33	6.12	6.44	6.12	5.29	6.14	6.14	6.30
Jute	0.40	0.38	0.38	0.36	0.35	0.34	0.33	0.30
Mesta	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03
Total Fibers	6.80	6.56	6.88	6.54	5.71	6.55	6.52	6.64
Tobacco	0.22	0.22	0.21	0.24	0.21	0.21	0.20	0.19
Other Crops	6.67	6.70	7.04	7.29	6.35	6.32	6.15	5.72
Gross Cropped Area	100.00							

Source: Agriculture Statistics at a Glance 2022

Extent of Crop diversification

For the second part of objective in the paper i.e., understanding the extent or magnitude of Crop Diversification in India, we will use the Herfindahl-Hirschman’s Index (HHI) and Simpson’s Index of Diversification (SID), henceforth HHI and SID respectively. The HHI index is defined as a sum of squares of all ‘n’ proportions (Saha, 2013). This is a simple measure of concentration. For increasing diversification, HHI is decreasing and vice-versa. The HHI index was calculated using equation (1).

$$HHI = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i^2 \tag{1}$$

Where, $P_i = \frac{x_i}{\sum x_i}$

Here,

p_i denotes the proportion of the i^{th} crop/crop sector in the gross cropped area. The diversification index ranges between 0 and 1, with lower values indicating a high degree of diversification and vice-versa.

The Simpson's Index of Diversification (SID), also referred to as the Simpson's Diversity Index or simply Simpson's Index, is a metric used to quantify the degree of diversity or concentration within a dataset. Simpson’s Index of Diversification is formulated from the Herfindahl-Hirschman’s Index. The formula for Simpson’s Index of diversification is given below in equation (2).

$$SID = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n p_i^2 \tag{2}$$

Where, $P_i = \frac{x_i}{\sum x_i}$

Here,

p_i denotes the proportion of the i^{th} crop/crop sector in the gross cropped area. A numerical value between 0 and 1 is provided by the index; higher values denote greater diversity and vice-versa which is completely opposite of Herfidahl-Hirschman’s Index.

For this study the Gross Cropped Area of major crops in million hectares (All India level) from the report of Economic Survey 2023-24 has been taken for our analysis. The total cropped area for major crops has increased from 439.2 million hectares in 2014-15 to 462.1 million hectares in 2023-24 (Table 4). The data from table 4 has been utilized for calculating the Herfindahl-Hirschman's Index (HHI) and Simpson's Index of Diversification (SID) during the period 2014-15 to 2023-24.

Table 4: Gross Area Under Major Crops (Million Hectares)

Group/Commodity	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24*
Foodgrains	124.3	123.2	129.2	127.5	124.8	127.0	129.8	130.2	132.2	130.2
Cereals	100.7	98.3	99.8	97.7	95.6	99.0	101.0	99.4	103.3	103.2
Nutri / Coarse Cereals	25.2	24.4	25.0	24.3	22.1	24.0	24.1	22.7	24.1	24.4
Pulses	23.6	24.9	29.4	29.8	29.2	28.0	28.8	30.7	28.9	27.0
Rice	44.1	43.5	44.0	43.8	44.2	43.7	45.8	46.3	47.8	47.6
Wheat	31.5	30.4	30.8	29.7	29.3	31.4	31.1	30.5	31.4	31.2
Jowar	6.2	6.1	5.6	5.0	4.1	4.8	4.4	3.8	3.5	4.0
Bajra	7.3	7.1	7.5	7.5	7.1	7.5	7.7	6.8	7.6	7.4
Maize	9.2	8.8	9.6	9.4	9.0	9.6	9.9	10.0	10.7	10.7
Tur	3.9	4.0	5.3	4.4	4.6	4.5	4.7	4.9	4.1	4.1
Gram	8.3	8.4	9.6	10.6	9.6	9.7	10.0	10.7	10.5	9.5
Oilseeds	25.6	26.1	26.2	24.5	24.8	27.1	28.8	29.0	30.2	30.1
Groundnut	4.8	4.6	5.3	4.9	4.7	4.8	6.0	5.7	5.0	4.7
Rapeseed and Mustard	5.8	5.7	6.1	6.0	6.1	6.9	6.7	8.0	8.9	9.1
Sugarcane	5.1	4.9	4.4	4.7	5.1	4.6	4.9	5.2	5.9	5.6
Cotton	12.8	12.3	10.8	12.6	12.6	13.5	13.3	12.4	12.9	12.7
Jute and Mesta	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.6
Total cropped area under major crops	439.2	433.5	449.4	443.1	433.6	446.8	457.7	457.0	467.7	462.1

Source: Economic Survey 2023-24

The HHI index has been continuously falling during the period 2014-15 to 2023-24 from 0.1601 to 0.1570 (Table 5). Whereas, in the same time period SID has moved up from 0.8399 in 2014-15 to 0.8424 in 2023-24. As discussed earlier, both HHI and SID indicate diversification. But they do so by giving values opposite of each other. Since, HHI is moving towards '0' it indicates more diverse nature of cropping pattern. This same trend of diversification is corroborated by Simpson's Index of Diversification (SID) which shows the

index moving towards '1'. So it can be said that the magnitude or extent of crop diversification has been increasing continuously over time.

Table 5: Crop Diversification Indicated by Herfindahl-Hirschman's Index Simpson's Index of Diversification

Years	Herfindahl-Hirschman's index	Simpson's Index of Diversification
2014-15	0.1601	0.8399
2015-16	0.1598	0.8402
2016-17	0.1595	0.8405
2017-18	0.1590	0.8410
2019-20	0.1595	0.8423
2020-21	0.1577	0.8428
2021-22	0.1572	0.8430
2022-23	0.1570	0.8429
2023-24	0.1571	0.8424

Source: Author's own calculation from Table 4

Figure 2 and 3 represent the HHI index and SID index respectively. The HHI index continuously gives a downward trend with a little spike in 2019-20. But overall the HHI index has a negative trend line. The SID index gives a positive slope for the entire time period. Since both the indexes provide the same result it can be concluded that crop diversification within the major crops that are cultivated has actually increased over time.

Figure 2: Herfindahl-Hirschman's Index

Source: Author's analysis using calculated value of Table 5

Figure 3: Simpson’s Index of Diversification

Source: Author’s analysis using calculated value of Table 5

The aforementioned method of Herfindahl’s-Hirschman’s Index and Simpson’s Index was applied to three sub-categories of crops i.e., foodgrains, oilseeds and horticultural crops. The previous analysis considered individual major crops whereas here magnitude diversification of three sub-categories of crops will be determined. It is evident from table 6 that overall the area under cultivation has increased from 2009-10 to 2020-21. For determining the extent of diversification the proportionate area of each category of crops needs to be considered within this time frame.

Table 6: Area under three sub-categories of Crops (thousand hectares)

Year	Foodgrains		Oilseeds		Horticulture		Total Area Cultivated for three category of Crops (000’ hectares)
	Area Cultivated (000’ hectares)	Percentage of the total area cultivated	Area Cultivated (000’ hectares)	Percentage of the total area cultivated	Area Cultivated (000’ hectares)	Percentage of the total area cultivated	
2009-10	121340	72.15%	25960	15.44%	20876	12.41%	168176
2010-11	126670	72.09%	27220	15.49%	21825	12.42%	175715
2011-12	124750	71.57%	26310	15.09%	23242	13.33%	174302
2012-13	120780	70.65%	26480	15.49%	23694	13.86%	170954
2013-14	125040	70.53%	28050	15.82%	24198	13.65%	177288
2014-15	124300	71.72%	25600	14.77%	23410	13.51%	173310
2015-	123220	70.90%	26090	15.01%	24472	14.08%	173782

16							
2016-17	129230	71.69%	26180	14.52%	24851	13.79%	180261
2017-18	127520	71.94%	24510	13.83%	25236	14.24%	177266
2018-19	124780	71.18%	24790	14.14%	25737	14.68%	175307
2019-20	126990	70.31%	27140	15.03%	26482	14.66%	180612
2020-21	129800	69.75%	28830	15.49%	27476	14.76%	186106

Source: Author’s consolidation from Agriculture Statistics at a Glance 2022 & Horticultural Statistics at a Glance 2021

The magnitude of diversification is unsubstantial when sub-categories of crops (foodgrains, oilseeds and horticultural crops) are considered. Unlike the analysis for major crops where HHI index moved towards ‘0’ indicating greater diversification here the HHI index remained in the half way point between 0 and 1 (Table 7). Though HHI index has shown a downward trend from 2009-10 to 2020-21 which should indicate cropping pattern moving towards diversification yet the index values are quite insignificant to be concluded that high diversification has taken place (Figure 4). Similar results were found while using Simpson’s Index of Diversification.

Table 7: Extent of Diversification in three Categorical Crops (Foodgrains, Oilseeds and Horticultural crops)

Year	Herfindahl Index	Simpson's Index
2009-10	0.5598	0.4402
2010-11	0.5591	0.4409
2011-12	0.5528	0.4472
2012-13	0.5424	0.4576
2013-14	0.5411	0.4589
2014-15	0.5545	0.4455
2015-16	0.5451	0.4549
2016-17	0.5541	0.4459
2017-18	0.5569	0.4431
2018-19	0.5482	0.4518
2019-20	0.5384	0.4616
2020-21	0.5322	0.4678

Source: Author’s own calculation using data of Table 6

Figure 4: Categorical Crop (Foodgrains, Oilseeds and Horticultural crops)

Source: Author's own analysis from table 7

Extent of Agriculture Diversification

Beginning in the early 1990s, the neo-liberal strategies that drove India's economy toward globalization caused a change in the pattern of agriculture sector. From 2011-12 to 2022-23 the share of crops in the Gross Value Added (GVA) at current prices has declined, whereas, that of Fisheries and Livestocks have increased (Table 1). Here, Herfindahl-Hirschman's Index was applied to determine the extent of diversification within agriculture and allied activities. Instead of proportionate area under each sub-sector we have utilized the value of output at current prices to determine the extent or magnitude of diversification within sub-sectors (Table 2). The HHI index from 2011-12 to 2021-22 produced insignificant values which estimates that there is low level of diversification within agriculture sub-sectors. However, the values of HHI index declined from 0.4631 to 0.4036 within the time period assessed (Table 6). On plotting the HHI index in a line diagram a downward trend line was achieved which indicates that agriculture sector is slowly moving towards diversification and the magnitude of this diversification may increase in the future (Figure 5).

Table 8: Sub-sectoral Diversification of Agriculture and Allied Activities

Year	Herfindahl Index
2011-12	0.4631
2012-13	0.4579
2013-14	0.4573
2014-15	0.4390
2015-16	0.4255
2016-17	0.4213
2017-18	0.4147
2018-19	0.4029
2019-20	0.4061
2020-21	0.4047
2021-22	0.4036

Source: Authors own calculation using data of Table 2

Figure 5: Herfindahl-Hirschman’s Index for Agriculture Diversification

Source: Author’s own analysis from table 8

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, India has had favourable diversification in the agricultural and crop sectors over the course of the last ten years. This expansion in pulses, fruits, vegetables, and high-value crops reflects an increase in the variety of agricultural processes, despite the fact that the proportion of GCA that is comprised of staples such as rice, wheat and other cereals has remained considerable throughout the course of time. It is thus a confirmation of crop diversification as well as agricultural diversification, as both HHI and SID demonstrate. The former reveals a general trend of moving downhill, while the latter

indicates a tendency towards greater values. It can be deduced from this that the agricultural sector in India is gradually transitioning towards a model that is more robust and sustainable in terms of the sources of and threats presented by external shocks resulting from climate change, market volatility, and other forms. As a result of increased diversity, farmers are less reliant on a particular crop, which in turn helps the stability of their revenues. The continuation of support from government policies and initiatives that promote diversification, particularly in the direction of high-value crops, sustainable practices, and climate-resilient technologies, will be essential for further improvement in the overall productivity and economic sustainability in the Indian agricultural sector. This will be especially important in the direction of climate-resilient technologies.

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